

Manuscript Checklist for Reviewer Vol 9, Issue 10 OCT-2020**Paper Title****Some Aspects of Lebanon's International Economy****Author Details:****Vincenzo Palumbo Chiara Villani**

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Title	Comments
Is it suitable? Dose it reflect the content?	Yes
Can it be improved?	NO
Abstract	Comments
Is it informative? Are the main results and conclusions mentioned?	Yes – Conclusion given
Keywords	Comments
Are keywords provided?	Yes
Introduction	Comments
Are the aims clear?	Yes
Methods	Comments
Are they adequately explained?	Yes well explained
Results	Comments
Are they described? Is any amplification or pruning necessary?	Discussion given
Discussion	Comments
Has this sufficient depth?	Yes
Conclusions	Comments
Do they follow from the evidence presented?	Yes
Referencing	Comments
Are there important missing references?	No
Originality	Comments
Dose it contain sufficiently new results, ideas or techniques?	Yes
Scope	Comments
Is it interdisciplinary in scope and of more than local interest?	Yes
Implications	Comments
Is the broader context clear?	Yes very clear
Language	Comments
Is it written fluent English?	Yes in fluent English

Organization	Comments
Is it well organized?	Yes , Organized
Tables/Figures	Comments
Are there to many tables/figures (normal max 8 for paper)?	Yes Given Properly
Are they necessary and well design?	Yes
Will they be legible on reduction?	Legible
Is there a list of table/figure captions? (on a separate sheet)	No
Overall evaluation (Tick the most appropriate for your decision)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent [✓]	Present an important new approach, new ideas or new information.
<input type="checkbox"/> Good	Improves significantly on previous work of its type or contains new interesting information
<input type="checkbox"/> Average	Good work but contains little novelty and may be of limited interest to more readers
<input type="checkbox"/> Routine	No errors, but likely to be of interest to local readers, not of international interest.
<input type="checkbox"/> Flawed	Contains serious flaws in e.g., project designs, data analysis or presentations
Recommendation (Tick whichever is applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Accept subject to minor revision. Not requiring reconsideration by referees. [✓] <input type="checkbox"/> Possibly acceptable after moderate revision. Possibly requiring reconsideration by referees. <input type="checkbox"/> Not accepted, major revision required. Possibly with the opportunity resubmission. <input type="checkbox"/> More suitable for publication in a different journal. <input type="checkbox"/> Not acceptable for publication in the IJMSBR .	
General Comments:	
In next papers try to add Supervisor Comments.	

Comments from Internal Reviewer

Please fill a grade of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 (High to low)

Overall evaluation on the paper	3.6
Contribution to existing knowledge	4
Organization and Readability	4
Soundness of methodology	4
Evidence supports conclusion	3
Adequacy of literature review	3

Comments and Suggestions

Editor has to organize to format for article.

Comments from External Reviewer

Evaluation Grade

Please fill a grade of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 (High to low)

Overall evaluation on the paper	3.4
Contribution to existing knowledge	4
Organization and Readability	3
Soundness of methodology	4
Evidence supports conclusion	3
Adequacy of literature review	3